

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OSTEOPLASTIC MATERIAL OSTEON COLLAGEN 3 AFTER IMMEDIATE IMPLANTATION PROCEDURE

Alexander Valentinovich Zhdanov

Tashkent State Dental Institute

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Abstract: Immediat Implantation method is currently a new trend in the field of dental implantation, but it is in great demand among implantologists. However, this procedure raises many questions related to the primary stabilization of the implant, as well as the choice of bone substitute material to fill the spaces between the implant and the walls of the dental cavity to prevent possible resorption of the alveolus. All this creates prerequisites for the search and study of osteoplastic materials suitable for use in this method.

Keywords: . Immediat Implantation, OSTEON COLLAGEN 3 , one-stage tooth extraction, implant installations

Purpose of the study: To investigate the possibility of using the osteoplastic material OSTEON COLLAGEN 3 in Immediat Implantation method for one-stage tooth extraction and implant installation. To evaluate the effectiveness of this material after the process of regeneration in 9 months after the procedure by methods of histologic and radiographic study, ISQ registration of implants in the area of augmentation.

Materials and methods of research In the course of the conducted research at the Department of Surgical Dentistry and Dental Implantology (DDSI) the procedure of Immediat Implantation with one-stage implant installation (Dentium, Super line South. Korea)) and filling of free spaces in the well with augmentant Osteon Collagen 3 (South Korea) in the study group in 15 patients aged 30-45 years After the bone-plastic material was applied and the implant was installed, a gingiva shaper (Healing abutment) was placed on the implant. We recorded the results of the study after 9 months of regeneration by means of radiographic and histological analysis, as well as ISQ analysis during implantation and after the period of complete bone regeneration with the augmentation and its integration with the implant.

Results: after the histological and radiographic studies the complete regeneration of bone tissue was obtained, as well as complete filling of the defect with bone tissue according to the computerized radiography. The ISQ analysis revealed the increase of the implant stabilization in the augmentation area from 65 units (the average value in the group) up to 75 units. The histological analysis

obtained during the sampling of the patients of the studied group showed the areas of osteogenic, fibrous tissue of different intensity of compaction, moderate amount of osteoblasts.

Conclusions: based on the obtained data, we can confidently assert the possibility of effective application of the osteoplastic material Osteon Collagen 3 after the Immediat Implantation procedure to fill the voids around the implant. This material almost completely fills the deficit of the jaw bone tissue after the period of remodeling and regeneration and has approximate morpho-physiological characteristics of native bone tissue.

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